

Annex D – List of participants

Last Name	First Name	Role in the Workshop	Name of employer	Country of employment
Charistou	Agathi	Core organising team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Coja	Tamara	Core organising team	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria
Souvlidis	Vasilis	Core organising team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Aagaard	Alf	Participant	Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA)	Denmark
Aggarwal	Manoj	Participant	Corteva Agriscience	United States of America
Amos Pedersen	Erik	Participant	Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA)	Denmark
Andersen	Hilde	Participant	Norwegian Environment Agency	Norway
Angeli	Karine	Participant	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES)	France
Arena	Maria	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Arente	Flera	Participant	State Plant Protection Service of the Republic of Latvia	Latvia
Astuto	Maria Chiara	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Bach	Ute	Participant	Bayer AG R&D Crop Science	Germany
Bars	Rémi	Participant	Regulatory Science Associates	United Kingdom
Bastaki	Maria	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy

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Batakis	Petros	Participant	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Battalora	Michael	Participant	FMC Corporation	United States of America
Bean	Thomas	Speaker	FMC Corporation	United States of America
Beekhuijzen	Manon	Speaker	Charles River Laboratories	Netherlands
Benford	Diane	Chair	EFSA Scientific Committee	United Kingdom
Berneron	Johanna	Participant	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES)	France
Bighiu	Maria	Participant	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Binaglia	Marco	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Blodörn	Krister	Participant	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Blystone	Chad	Speaker	National Toxicology Program (NTP)	United States of America
Bowen	Damian	Participant	ERM	United Kingdom
Bradley	Alys	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Breul	Lea	Participant	Environment Agency Austria	Austria
Brizzi	Stefano	Participant	BASF SE	Belgium
Bultman	Joanna	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United States of America
Büttner	Theresa	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	Germany
Cao	Sunice	Participant	BASF SE	China
Castoldi	Anna Federica	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Cavalier	Adeline	Speaker	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES)	France

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Chiusolo	Arianna	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Clausing	Peter	Speaker	PAN Europe	Germany
Conway	Louise	Participant	Health and Safety Authority (HSA)	Ireland
Corvaro	Marco	Participant	Corteva Agriscience	Italy
Cowe	Nyree	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Craig	Peter	Participant	Durham University	United Kingdom
Crivellente	Federica Adele	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Dammann	Martina	Participant	BASF SE	Germany
Davidson	Jutta	Speaker	Charles River Laboratories	Germany
Davis	Barbara	Participant	Nuseed Nutritional	United States of America
Debabrata	Kanungo	Participant	Personal capacity	India
Dertinger	Stephen	Speaker	Litron Laboratories	United States of America
Desprez	Bertrand	Speaker	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES)	France
Dodds	Jenifer	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Dunham	Lora	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Elliott	Claire	Participant	Penman Consulting	United Kingdom
Fatur	Tanja	Participant	National Institute of Public Health	Slovenia
Florida	Ebel	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	Ireland
Foudoulakis	Manousos	Speaker	Corteva Agriscience	Greece
Fritsche	Jens	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	Germany
Fryndelund	Jorid	Participant	Norwegian Environment Agency	Norway
Gadowska	Maria	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom

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Garcin	Jean-Christophe	Participant	Bayer AG R&D Crop Science	France
Geiser	Christoph	Participant	Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (FSVO)	Switzerland
Gioutlakis	Michail	Participant	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Gómez	Teresa	Participant	Ministry of Health	Spain
Gröters	Sibylle	Speaker	BASF SE	Germany
Hałajewska-Wosik	Anetta	Participant	Bureau for Chemical Substances	Poland
Hatzi	Vasia	Participant	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Hauzenberger	Ingrid	Participant	Environment Agency Austria	Austria
HAYAR	Salem	Participant	Personal capacity	Lebanon
Hernandez Jerez	Antonio	Participant	University of Granada	Spain
Hillebrand	Marcus	Participant	German Environment Agency (UBA)	Germany
Hodge-Bell	Kimberly	Participant	Bayer AG R&D Crop Science	United States of America
Hofmaier	Tina	Participant	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria
Hofmann	Thomas	Speaker	BASF SE	Germany
Hölzl	Christine	Participant	Environment Agency Austria	Austria
Houlihan	Margarete	Participant	Health and Safety Authority (HSA)	Ireland
Istace	Frederique	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Jackson	Ailsa	Participant	TSG Consulting	United Kingdom
Jacobsen	Pernille	Participant	Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA)	Denmark
Jaeh	Urte	Speaker	Charles River Laboratories	Germany

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Janušauskaitė	Dalia	Participant	The State Plant Service under the Ministry of Agriculture	Lithuania
Jensen	Stine	Participant	Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA)	Denmark
Jiménez-Ruiz	Jesús	Participant	INIA (CSIC)	Spain
Jørgensen	Nina Henriette	Participant	Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA)	Denmark
Kass	George	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Kiakos	Konstantinos	Participant	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)	Finland
Kienzler	Aude	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Kjærstad	Mia	Participant	Danish Environmental Protection Agency (DEPA)	Denmark
Kluxen	Felix	Participant	ADAMA Deutschland GmbH	Germany
Kostolaniova	Petra	Participant	CropLife Europe	Belgium
Kovács	Zsuzsanna	Participant	ELBC	Hungary
Kubincova	Petra	Participant	Research Institute for Organic Syntheses, Inc. (VUOS)	Czech Republic
Kührer	Lukas	Participant	Environment Agency Austria	Austria
Kyriakopoulou	Katerina	Project team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Lacroix	Marc	Participant	Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment	Belgium
Lagadic	Laurent	Participant	Bayer AG R&D Crop Science	Germany
Lanzoni	Anna	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Latsou	Konstantina Maria	Participant	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Lee	Sandy	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United States of America

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Lindberg	Hanna	Participant	Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes)	Finland
Lipscomb	Elizabeth	Participant	BASF SE	United States of America
Little	Joanne	Participant	Health and Safety Executive (HSE)	United Kingdom
Low	Kimberley	Participant	Health Canada	Canada
Luomahaara	Sirpa	Participant	Finnish Safety and Chemicals Agency (Tukes)	Finland
Ma	Eric	Participant	Syngenta	United States of America
Machera	Kyriaki	Project team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Mackay	Karen	Participant	Perstorp AB	Sweden
Madsen	Soren	Participant	WHO	Switzerland
Malme	Irene Beate Sørvik	Participant	Norwegian Food Safety Authority	Norway
Manton	Jason	Participant	Penman Consulting	United Kingdom
Manuel	Sanz Bernal	Participant	Ministry of Health	Spain
Marinovic	Marina	Participant	University of Milan	Italy
Martinenghi	Luca	Participant	Eurofins gmbh	Germany
Martino	Laura	Speaker	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Masood	Romaisa	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Matthies	Anastasia	Participant	Federal Office of Consumer protection and Food Safety	Germany
Mayerhofer	Ulrike	Project team	Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES)	Austria
McCann	Andrew	Participant	Gov.ie; Department of Agriculture	Ireland
McGuire	Aidan	Speaker	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Melching-Kollmuss	Stephanie	Participant	BASF SE	Germany

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Mendez	Elizabeth	Participant	Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA)	United States of America
Mentor	Anna	Participant	The Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Metruccio	Francesca	Participant	ASST Fatebenefratelli Sacco	Italy
Meurer	Krista	Participant	BASF SE	Germany
Mikles	Kathy	Participant	Corteva Agriscience	United States of America
Mohammed	Ifthekhar Ali	Participant	Swedish Chemicals Agency	Sweden
Moretto	Angelo	Participant	University of Padova	Italy
Nikolopoulou	Dimitra	Project team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Noakes	James	Participant	Regulatory Science Associates	United Kingdom
Noor	Mirza Nusrat	Participant	Perstorp AB	Sweden
O'Neill	Aoife	Participant	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	Ireland
Palovics	Agnes	Participant	National Food Safety Office	Hungary
Paltanavičiene	Audra	Participant	The State Plant Service under the Ministry of Agriculture	Lithuania
Pandya	Hirna	Participant	UPL limited	India
Panzarea	Martina	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Passamonti	Sabina	Participant	University of Trieste	Italy
Paxinou	Akrivi Chara	Participant	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Peczowska	Beata	Participant	Bureau for Chemical Substances	Poland
Pelizzari	Andrea	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	Italy
Perazzolo	Chiara	Speaker	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)	Finland
Petersen	Annika Boye	Participant	The Technical University of Denmark	Denmark

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Pieper	Christina	Participant	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)	Germany
Podevin	Nancy	Participant	Pioneer Overseas Corporation	Belgium
Pörtl	Gerald	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	Germany
Pribu	Mihaela	Participant	National Institute of Public Health	Romania
Printemps	Nathalie	Participant	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES)	France
Raveesha	KP	Participant	Eurofins Advinus	India
Redmond	Aisling	Participant	UPL limited	Ireland
Repouskou	Anastasia	Participant	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Richmond	Emily	Participant	Exponent International	United Kingdom
Rignall	Benjamin	Participant	BASF SE	Germany
Rizov	Ivelin	Participant	Ministry of Agriculture	Bulgaria
Rogerson	Petrina	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United Kingdom
Rongved	Tonje Danielsen	Participant	Norwegian Environment Agency	Norway
Roper	Jason	Participant	Corteva Agriscience	United States of America
Roth	Markus	Participant	SCC GmbH – Scientific Consulting Company	Germany
Ruckman	Stephen	Participant	TSG Consulting	United Kingdom
Rudzok	Susanne	Speaker	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)	Germany
Satoshi	Asano	Participant	Food Safety Commission of Japan	Japan
Schmitt	Anne	Participant	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)	Germany
Sharp	Rachel	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy

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Simoes	Ricardo	Participant	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)	Finland
Sonnenburg	Anna	Participant	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR)	Germany
Spilioti	Eliana	Project team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Spjuth	Linda	Participant	European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)	Finland
Spyropoulou	Anastasia	Project team	Benaki Phytopathological Institute (BPI)	Greece
Stier	Agnes	Participant	National Food Safety Office	Hungary
Strauss	Volker	Speaker	BASF SE	Germany
Stump	Donald	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United States of America
Tanchevski	Evelyn	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United States of America
Tarres Call	Jordi	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Terron	Andrea	Participant	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Tiramani	Manuela	Chair	European Food Safety Agency (EFSA)	Italy
Tokar	Stephanie	Participant	UPL limited	Canada
Tordoir	Charlotte	Participant	Federal public service Health, Food chain safety and Environment	Belgium
Tosti	Luca	Participant	University of Milan	Italy
Totlandsdal	Annike	Participant	Norwegian Food Safety Authority	Norway
Tyson	Kathy	Participant	Charles River Laboratories	United States of America
Varnai	Veda Marija	Participant	Institute for Medical Research and Occupational Health	Croatia
Vleminckx	Christiane	Participant	Sciensano	Belgium

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Waalkens-Berendsen	Ine	Participant	FAF Panel member	Netherlands
Wang	Wendy	Participant	FMC Corporation	United States of America
Wheeler	James	Participant	Corteva Agriscience	Netherlands
Wilks	Martin	Chair	Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology	Switzerland
Wisniewska	Iwona	Participant	Merit Mark Polska (Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)	Poland
Wohlman	Irene	Participant	FMC Corporation	United States of America
Yoshida	Midori	Participant	Personal capacity	Japan
Zarn	Jürg	Participant	Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (FSVO)	Switzerland
Zlochova	Tereza	Participant	National Institute of Public Health, Department of Chemical Safety	Czech Republic
Zürcher	Ursina	Participant	Federal Food Safety and Veterinary Office (FSVO)	Switzerland